

THE CHANDERI INSCRIPTION OF 'ALĀU'D-DĪN KHALJĪ

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The inscription of 'Alāu'd-Dīn Khaljī, which I have selected for comments in this article, came to light more than four decades ago, and was, as a matter of fact, even published with historical notes and an illustration. It was first listed in one of the reports of the Archaeological Department of the erstwhile Gwalior State,¹ and its photographic reproduction was entrusted by the Director of the said Department to Mr. Ram Singh Saksena, who published it with a detailed note as early as in 1925.² Unfortunately, Mr. Saksena's study not only lacks scientific treatment, but also suffers from certain inaccuracies and consequent mis-statements, which may be termed as quite serious, and it is rather surprising that these should have remained uncorrected so far. Having had occasion to make a brief reference to these lapses while listing this epigraph in our Annual Report, I now take this opportunity to make its correct purport available to scholars by re-editing it here.

The epigraphical tablet, which is of soft white sandstone, measures 127 by 45 cm. and was originally found, and it still is, in the house of one Parbho Dayāl, a Brahmin resident of the town of Chanderi,³ which was once the provincial capital under the Sultāns of Malwa. Now considerably reduced in importance, except for its cotton *sāris*, it is denied even the status of a *taba'īl* headquarters. The slab is built into one of the walls of the said house, but it is neither known, nor has it been possible to ascertain, how or when it came to be fixed into its present place. That it originally belonged to a place of worship, is quite clear from the text and needs no further confirmation. On the other hand, I am informed by my colleague Shri S. A. Rahim, who got its rubbings prepared, that the building in which the tablet occurs, is just an ordinary residential unit, without the slightest pretension to antiquity or architectural merit, and therefore, there seems to be little doubt that the slab was brought from elsewhere, or that the original mosque on which it was fixed, must have existed in its vicinity.

The four-line text of the epigraph is cut in relief in *Naskh* style. While its calligraphy cannot be said to be of the finest order, it is nevertheless quite pleasing to the eye, mainly on account of its neat execution, which easily makes it one of the best executed records of the Khaljī monarch.

The text purports that a mosque was built in 1312, during the reign of the great king, the Alexander of the age, 'Alāu'd-Dīn Muḥammad Shāh and during the time of the governorship of Amīru'l-Umarā Ikhṭiyāru'd-Daulat wa'd-Dīn Tamur Sultānī, the champion (*pahlwān*) of Irān, by Ismā'īl, son of 'Abdu's-Salām, called Wajīh-i-Najīb. The builder is designated in the text as the *muharrir* (accountant),⁴ attached to the district (*khitta*)⁵ of Kol (i.e. modern Aligarh in Uttar Pradesh).

The major inaccuracies in Mr. Saksena's study were that firstly, he could not determine the name of the governor, having taken the word 'Tamur' to indicate its literary meaning of a sword,

¹ *Annual Report of the Archaeological Department, Gwalior State, 1924-25*, No. 10 of Appendix E.

² R. S. Saksena, 'Persian Inscriptions in the Gwalior State', *Indian Historical Quarterly*, vol. I (1925), pp. 655-56.

³ *Annual Report on Indian Epigraphy (ARIE)*, 1962-63, No. D, 59 and p. 36.

⁴ For a brief note on the exact connotation of this term, see *Epigraphia Indica, Arabic and Persian Supplement (ELAPS)*, 1967, p. 13.

⁵ For a note on the meaning of the term *khitta*, please see p. 10, *infra*.

and secondly, having read the place-name 'Kol' as a personal name 'Kok', he sought to identify that imaginary person with the Malwa king Koka. His observations occupying a greater part of his article, based as they are on these incorrect readings, are naturally wrong and misleading, as will be presently pointed out.

The text, as deciphered by me, is quoted below .—

TEXT

Plate I(b)

- (۱) عمارت این مسجد در عهد مملکت سلطان المعظم علاء الدنيا و الدين اسکندر الزمان
ابو المظفر محمد شاه
- (۲) السلطان خلد الله ملكه و سلطانه و اعلى امره و شانہ و در وقت نيابت امير الامرا
- (۳) ملجاء الكبرا اختيار الدولة و الدين پهلوان ايران تمر سلطانی ادا م الله معاليه و
زيد دولته
- (۴) بنده اميدوار رحمت دار [ا] لسلام اسمعيل بن عبد السلام الملقب وجيه نجيب محرر
منسوب بخطه كول تمام كرد بيستم از ماه شعبان سنة احدى عشر و سبعماية

TRANSLATION

(1) The construction of this mosque (took place) in the reign of the kingdom of the magnificent Sultān 'Alāu'd-Dunyā wa'd-Dīn (lit. Glory of the State and Religion), Iskandar (i.e. Alexander) of the Time, Abu'l-Muzaffar Muḥammad Shāh,

(2) the Sultān, may Allāh perpetuate his kingdom and sovereignty, and elevate his affairs and position, and in the time of the deputy-ship (*niyābat*) of Amīru'l-Umarā (lit. the chief among the chiefs),

(3) the refuge of the great, Ikh̄tiyāru'd-Daulat wa'd-Dīn, the champion (*pahlwān*) of Irān, Tamur Sultānī, may Allāh perpetuate his glories and increase his fortune !

(4) The creature, hopeful of (attaining) the mercy in the House of Peace (namely), Ismā'il, son of 'Abdu's-Salām, called Wajih-i-Najīb, the *muharrir* attached to the District (*khitta*) of Kol, completed it (on) the twentieth of the month of Sha'bān, year (A.H.) eleven and seven hundred (20 Sha'bān 711=1 January 1312).

A comparison of the above-quoted text and translation with those of Mr. Saksena will reveal a number of mistakes in decipherment, most of them minor, and in translation too; for obvious reasons, indicating these mistakes is avoided here. But as already stated above, one of the major inaccuracies of Mr. Saksena's study resulted from his inability to determine the name of the governor, whose titles and name are given in the text as 'Ikh̄tiyāru'd-Daulat wa'd-Dīn Pahlwān-i-Irān Tamur Sultānī'. According to Mr. Saksena, this whole phrase which he translated as 'the lord (paramount) of the fortune of Religion, the greatest athlete', only contained the honorific titles of the governor, but not his name. This omission he tried to explain away thus: 'The name of the Governor whose titles only cover more than a line of the inscription seems to have slipped from

the pen of the writer, and which he might have thought of inserting somewhere amidst the titles'.¹ This reasoning is, to put it mildly, rather curious: the composer, or for that matter even the scribe or engraver, may altogether omit the name of the governor, but it is highly improbable that in the text of a record, the name of any person intended to be mentioned, particularly of the status of a governor, should slip from the engraver's pen.

The fact is that it did not strike Mr. Saksena that the word Tamur, a common noun in Turkish, meaning 'a sword', is used here not as such, but as a proper noun, as it is also indicated respectively by the appellation Sultānī and the high titles including the personal one *Ikh̄tiyāru'd-Dīn*, indicating his status, that follow and precede the name. Then again, a reference to contemporary historical works would have provided a clue to the name of this high nobleman who finds mention therein.

Secondly, Mr. Saksena has erred in reporting Ismā'il, son of 'Abdu's-Salām, as one 'who wrote this epigraph', though he correctly credits him with having 'caused the mosque completed'.² This mistake was again due to his wrong reading of the word *mansūb* in the phrase *muḥarrir-i-mansūb ba-kh̄itta-i-Kol* in the third line, as *maktūb*; this phrase (as read by him) he had translated as 'writer of the script (caused it to be completed), in the country of Koka'.³ The fact is that Ismā'il was the *muḥarrir* (secretary)⁴ attached to the *kh̄itta* (district) of Kol, i.e. modern Aligarh. Since he failed to establish the correct purport of the text, Mr. Saksena was in doubt about Ismā'il's vocation, as is clear from his statement that 'he seems to be in all probability either an architect or some subordinate officer who might be in charge of the construction of the mosque'.⁵

Thirdly, Mr. Saksena states that the 'inscription names no town but mentions the territory of Koka.....the Raja of Malwa'.⁶ The text, as we have seen above, mentions Kol and not Koka and states that the builder of the mosque was an official of that district. Consequently, Mr. Saksena's surmise that 'it is probable that even at that time (i.e. in 1311, seven years after the *Kh̄aljī* conquest of Malwa despite Koka's valiant opposition), this part of the country may have been more popularly known as Koka dominion (Desa)', deserves to be rejected as it is not at all corroborated, even indirectly, by the text. Likewise, it would not be correct to maintain, as done by him, that the inscription provides a further evidence of the existence of the Malwa Rāja who has been noticed by *Firish̄ta* only.⁷ As a matter of fact, Koka, who was, incidentally, the foster-brother and prime-minister of the Malwa king, is mentioned by earlier writers, as for example, contemporary Amir *Khusraw* and later *Yahyā Sarhindī*.⁸

So much for Mr. Saksena's observations on this inscription. We have already seen above that the governor Tamur Sultānī is not unknown to history, though as in the case of most of the men of the past, we do not know much about him. Contemporary historian *Baranī* lists him among the nobles of 'Alāu'd-Dīn *Kh̄aljī* and his son *Quṭbu'd-Dīn Mubārak Shāh* and quotes both his name and title.⁹ He also mentions his having received the fief of *Chanderi* and *Erichh* from 'Alāu'd-Dīn.¹⁰

¹ Saksena, *op. cit.*, p. 654.

² *Ibid.*

³ *Ibid.*, p. 655.

⁴ For two more inscriptions referring to the office of the *muḥarrir*, please see *EIAPS*, 1964, p. 5; 1967, p. 13.

⁵ Saksena, *op. cit.*, p. 655.

⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 654.

⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 655.

⁸ Amir *Khusraw*, *Kh̄azā'inu't-Futūh* (Calcutta, 1953), pp. 55, 56; *Yahyā Sarhindī*, *Tārīkh-i-Mubārak Shāhī* (Calcutta 1931), p. 78.

⁹ *Divān'd-Dīn Baranī*, *Tārīkh-i-Firūz Shāhī* (Calcutta, 1862), pp. 241 (where the title is spelt as جبار الدين, an obvious misprint, which has not been corrected in the Hindi translation of the relevant portion in S.A.A. Rizvi, *Kh̄aljī-kālin Bhārat*, Aligarh, 1955, p. 41), 379.

¹⁰ *Baranī*, *op. cit.*, p. 323.

According to Amīr Khusraw, another contemporary historian, Tamur continued to hold the fief in the time of Mubārak Shāh as well.¹ In the latter's reign, he participated in the Warangal and Ma'bar expedition under Khusraw Khān, during which he and other nobles reported Khusraw Khān's secret designs to usurp the throne to the king, who, on the contrary, being under the evil influence of Khusraw Khān, punished them. As a result Tamur was dismissed, and his fief, transferred to Khusraw Khān.² Incidentally, the fact that the fief of Chanderi was deemed worthy to be conferred on Khusraw Khān indicates the high status of its holders, Malik Tamur being one.

But Malik Tamur seems to have managed to cast off his disgrace before long. He must have regained his status on the accession of Ghiyāthu'd-Dīn Tughluq Shāh, if not earlier, for we find him assisting Prince Jūnā, later on Sultān Muḥammad bin Tughluq, in his Telangana expedition. Here, too, forced by the circumstances similar to those just mentioned above—in which he and other nobles were charged with rebellious motives—he fled the Prince's army, after having obtained safe conduct from Rudra Deva, but pursued by the royal troops, ultimately perished at the hands of the local chiefs in Kalyani.³

It will strike one as curious that Malik Tamur and his colleagues should be concerned in strikingly similar events concerning two men of different temperaments under almost similar circumstances. It may be held to be nothing more than a mere coincidence, but it is rather hard to believe that in the two episodes referred to above, the behaviour of these nobles, including Malik Tamur, was motivated only by their sense of loyalty to Quṭbu'd-Dīn or Tughluq Shāh. Very likely, there was something erratic in their temperament which influenced their attitude and behaviour towards the generals under whom they were then working. This strong possibility has suggested itself to me on the basis of a statement of almost a contemporary of Malik Tamur, namely Mir Khurd, the celebrated author of *Siyaru'l-Auliya*. Mir Khurd speaks of a commotion raised by 'Tamur the governor of Chanderi', as a result of which a large number of men in his army, who were the disciples of the great saint of Delhi, Ḥadrāt Nizāmu'd-Dīn Auliya, migrated to other parts of the country.⁴ This, if at all, might represent some erratic streak in Tamur's nature.

It may be worthwhile to point out here that history does not record the exact time of the conquest of Chanderi region. It is generally believed to have been reduced along with Dhar and Ujjain by 'Ainu'l-Mulk soon after his conquest of Mandu in 1305,⁵ but no authority is quoted for this statement. No one among the contemporary historians, Khusraw, Barani, or 'Iṣāmī, refers specifically to the conquest of Chanderi itself. Even Yaḥyā Sarhindī, writing more than a century later, does not mention Chanderi's conquest either by 'Ainu'l-Mulk or any one else. Only Firishṭa refers to the capture of Chanderi, along with, and not after, that of Ujjain, Dhārānagarī (i.e. Dhar), and Mandu.⁶ Now it is very likely that Chanderi had, at that period, nothing to do with Malwa or at least with Dhar and Mandu; it seems to have formed an independent administrative unit, a province, different from that of Dhar and Mandu. This is also clear from

¹ Amīr Khusraw, *Nuh-Sipihr* (Bombay, 1950), p. 100.

² Barani, *op. cit.*, pp. 400-01; Dr. Agha Mahdi Husain, *Tughluq Dynasty* (Calcutta, 1963), pp. 31-32; K. S. Lal, *History of the Khaljis* (Allahabad, 1950), pp. 340-41.

³ Barani, *op. cit.*, pp. 448-49. He neither specifies the king's name, nor the name of the place where Tamur's army perished. But 'Iṣāmī gives more details in his *Futūhu's-Salāṭīn* (Madras, 1948), pp. 392-99, about the whole episode and places his destruction in or around Kalyani (*ibid.*, p. 399). Also see Mahdi Husain, *op. cit.*, pp. 64-65.

⁴ Mir Khurd, *Siyaru'l-Auliya* (Delhi, 1876), p. 286.

⁵ A. Cunningham, *Archaeological Survey of India Reports*, vol. II (Simla, 1871), p. 402, giving 1304; Saksena, *op. cit.*, p. 655; Lal, *op. cit.*, p. 134; Ibn Baṭṭūṭa, *The Rihla*, Eng. tr. Dr. Agha Mahdi Husain (Baroda, 1953), p. 166, f.n.3; Dr. R. C. Majumdar, ed. *The Delhi Sultanate* (Bombay, 1960), p. 29.

⁶ Firishṭa, *Tārīkh-i-Firishṭa* (Kanpur, 1881), p. 155.

Barani's account of the distribution of fiefs: we are told that while Dhar and Ujjain were given to 'Ainu'l-Mulk, Chanderi and Erichh were conferred on Malik Tamur.¹ Also, from Ibn Battūta's statement, it can be reasonably inferred that the administrative unit of Chanderi was inclusive of the region around Gwalior too. Ibn Battūta, it may be pointed out, reports his meeting with the governor of Chanderi at Gwalior.²

The above point should not be lost sight of while discussing the time of Chanderi's subjugation by the Muslims. But for the short-lived conquest by Iltutmish's son Nāṣiru'd-Dīn Maḥmūd in 1251,³ the place seems to have defied Muslim authority. At least in the time of Jalālu'd-Dīn Fīrūz Khaljī (1290-96), it was under Hindu sway, as is known from a categorical statement of 'Alāu'd-Dīn himself in the context of his Deogiri expedition from Kara.⁴ It must have been, therefore, reduced some time after that event, that is to say in the time of 'Alāu'd-Dīn. We can safely dismiss Ibn Battūta's statement that it was conquered by Khusraw Khān;⁵ he was probably misinformed or rather misled by the fact that Quṭbu'd-Dīn Mubārak Shāh had bestowed Chanderi on Khusraw Khān after Malik Tamur's dismissal, as has been seen above.

Thus the question as to when and by whom was Chanderi conquered remains still unanswered. Among the early authorities, only Mīr Khurd refers to the conquest of Chanderi having taken place in the reign of 'Alāu'd-Dīn. According to him, a governor (*wālī*), who was a disciple of the patron-saint of Delhi, Ḥaḍrat Nizāmu'd-Dīn, was sent by the king with a large force to conquer Chanderi. Since the assignment was a difficult one, the said official requested the saint to send one of his companions for moral and spiritual support, and accordingly, Maulānā Wajīhu'd-Dīn Yūsuf was deputed to participate in the expedition.⁶ Unfortunately, Mīr Khurd has refrained from either naming the governor or dating the event, though it is almost certain that the governor concerned was not Tamur, since the said hagiographer narrates this event immediately after he has referred to the high-handedness of Tamur (referred to in the preceding lines), resulting in the desertion of Chanderi by most of his soldiers and the intended desertion by Maulānā Yūsuf too.⁷ Under the circumstances, the only thing that can be definitely asserted is that Chanderi was conquered quite some time before A. H. 711, the date of our record.

Incidentally, the name Tamur is variously spelt by different writers as Tamar,⁸ Tamūr, Tamur or Timur,¹⁰ and Timūr.¹¹ As the name is inscribed in our epigraph without diacritical marks, it is difficult to determine the correct pronunciation. The name can be read both as 'Tamar' or 'Timur' in Arabic, the former meaning a 'ripe date', and the latter, the eye-disease—'a pearl in the eye' or 'obscurity and darkness'.¹² But in Turkish, the same word is pronounced

¹ Barani, *op. cit.*, p. 323.

² Ibn Battūta, *op. cit.*, pp. 152, 167.

³ Minhāj-i-Sirāj, *Tabaqāt-i-Nāṣirī* (Lahore, 1952), p. 122.

⁴ Barani, *op. cit.*, p. 220.

⁵ Ibn Battūta, *op. cit.*, p. 45.

⁶ Mīr Khurd, *op. cit.*, pp. 280-87.

Ibid., p. 286.

⁷ Majumdar, *op. cit.*, p. 43; Lal, *op. cit.*, pp. 230, 341; Rizvi, *op. cit.*, pp. 89, 135, 136, 225; Mahdi Husain, *op. cit.*, pp. 31-32, 65-66 (but 'Timūr' on pp. 67-68 and 'Tamar (Timūr)' on p. 67, f.n.3). In Dr. Mahdi Husain's English translation of Ibn Battūta's *Rihla* (p. 50), the name is spelt as Tamūr.

⁸ Ibn Battūta, *op. cit.*, p. 50.

¹⁰ 'Iṣāmī, *op. cit.*, pp. 392, 393, 394, 398.

¹¹ Mahdi Husain, *op. cit.*, pp. 67-68.

¹² Muhammad Bādshāh, *Farhang-i-Anandrāj*, vol. I (Lucknow, 1889), p. 731.

Timur which is stated to be the actual phonetic expression of the word written with long vowels i.e. Timūr and which means 'steel'.¹ On the other hand, according to 'Abdu'l-Hayy Ḥabībī, an Afghān scholar, who has recently published *Ṭabaqāt-i-Nāṣirī* of Minhāj-i-Sirāj from Kabul, 'the word spelt as Tamur, has been stated by Kāshgharī to mean steel, and the same spelling is given in the *Ṭabaqāt* in the names Tamurchī, Tamur Khān Qirān and Tamur Khān Sangar. However, the spelling of this name in the later times became Timūr, at times written as Tamūr. In Turkish, the term 'Damor' meaning iron or steel is nothing but a form of this 'Tamur'.² There is therefore little doubt that the correct pronunciation of the name is Tamur or Timur only. That the second syllable is *mur* is also corroborated by 'Iṣāmī who uses it as a rhyme of *pur*,³ which shows that the pronunciation, as he knew or heard it, was Tamur or Timur. Incidentally, the editor of the Madras edition of 'Iṣāmī's *Futūḥu's-Salāṭīn* has throughout transcribed the name as Timur.⁴

It may also be mentioned here that Tamur is mentioned as the *muqṭi'* of Chanderi by Baranī,⁵ as 'āmīl, by Ḥājji Dabīr⁶ and as *wālī*, by Mīr Khurd.⁷ This would mean that the terms *muqṭi'*, 'āmīl and *wālī* were considered more or less synonymous. ⁸

About Ismā'il, whom the text credits with the completion of the mosque, nothing is known from any other source. He was neither an architect nor the writer of the text nor a subordinate official in charge of the construction as was stated by Saksena. He was the *muḥarrir* attached to the district (*khitta*) of Kol or modern Aligarh, and was also commonly called (*almulaqqab*, lit. entitled, i.e. with nick-name) Wajih-i-Najīb. This last phrase, I feel, represents the second or popular names of both the son and father: in other words, 'Ismā'il was commonly called Wajih and his father, 'Abdu's-Salām, Najīb. Beyond the above information furnished by our record, nothing whatsoever is known about him.

Lastly, the epigraph under study is taken to furnish 'the earliest date so far known for the new site of Chanderi.'⁹ It has been presumed by A. Cunningham and later writers that it was Buri Chanderi, about 15 kilometres from the present town, which was conquered in 1304-05 by 'Alāu'd-Dīn's army.¹⁰ This assumption coupled with the fact that our inscription was found at modern Chanderi has been taken to mean that the new site came into existence some time between 1304-05, the date of the conquest of Chanderi and 1312, the date of the said record. Cunningham only bases his surmise on the fact that the Muslim historians—Ibn Baṭṭūṭa and Firishṭa—do not mention the fort of Chanderi but only the city and since the present city is fortified, 'Alāu'd-Dīn must have conquered the old city. This however, does not seem to be a strong presumption, and much stronger basis is needed to substantiate the statement that it was only old Chanderi that was conquered by 'Alāu'd-Dīn. On the other hand, it is not absolutely certain that the present tablet does belong to modern Chanderi; it was first, and even now, found in a private house, though it belonged to a mosque. Therefore, the assumption does not seem to be warranted by facts, and as such needs corroboration.

¹ Muḥammad Bādshāh, *op. cit.*, p. 779.

² Abdul-Hayy Ḥabībī, ed. *Ṭabaqāt-i-Nāṣirī* by Minhāj-i-Sirāj, vol. II (Kabul, 1343 Hijrī *Shamsī*), pp. 430-31.

³ 'Iṣāmī, *op. cit.* (Agra, 1938), p. 389 (verse 7389); *ibid.* (Madras, 1948), p. 398.

⁴ *Ibid.* (Madras), pp. 392, 393, 394, 398.

⁵ Baranī, *op. cit.*

⁶ Ḥājji Dabīr, *Zafaru'l-Wālīh bi-Muzaḥḥar wa-Ālīh*, part II (London, 1921), p. 845.

⁷ Mīr Khurd, *op. cit.*, p. 286.

⁸ For the views of Dr. Mahdi Husain on the functions of these posts, see Mahdi Husain, *op. cit.*, p. 31, l.n.3.

⁹ *Archaeological Survey of India, Annual Report (ARASI)*, 1924-25, p. 168.

¹⁰ Cunningham, *op. cit.*, pp. 402-03; *ARASI*, 1924-25, p. 168; Saksena, *op. cit.*; Mahdi Husain in Ibn Baṭṭūṭa, *op. cit.*, p. 166.

Before we conclude, a note on the term *khitta* may not be out of place here. The exact connotation of this word as used in inscriptions or elsewhere is difficult to determine. The literary meaning given thereof in the lexicographical work is 'a boundary or foundation-line of a house, a country, a territory, a region, a city, land occupied for the first time, a street, a habitation',¹ 'a boundary or foundation-line of a house',² or a land around which a boundary-line is drawn for the construction of a building to prevent encroachment, a piece of land,³ or 'the name by which a big (capital) city is generally known or is called in Arabia'.⁴ The term is loosely translated as a 'fortified city' or a 'territory,' 'district,' 'region' or 'province'. In the absence of any other information, it is difficult to establish the exact meaning for which it stands, but the meaning 'a district' or 'a territory' seems to be preferable to 'a fortified city'.

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- ¹ Francis Jhonson, *A Dictionary, Persian, Arabic and English* (London, 1852), p. 528.
- ² F. Steingass, *Comprehensive Persian-English Dictionary* (London, 1957), p. 467.
- ³ Muḥammad Bādshāh, *op. cit.*, vol. II (Lucknow, 1889), p. 1029; Ghiyāthu'd-Dīn, Ghiyāthu'l-Lughāt (Lucknow, 1895), p. 160.
- ⁴ *Ibid.* The printed text of Muḥammad Bādshāh's work has عرف i.e. in popular parlance, while that of Ghiyāthu'd-Dīn's has عرب i.e. in Arabia. The latter may be a mis-print.